

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AND THE ROLE OF INTEGRAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: Nowadays there is a growing necessity of highly qualified and flexible professionals. They have to possess a good knowledge of foreign languages to be able to communicate with colleagues from different countries. Thus, teachers of foreign language are in constant search for the most effective ways of training. In this paper, the authors analyze the process of teaching foreign (English) language to Bachelor students and identify the most effective ways of teaching communication in professional sphere. The study use a critical analysis of the literature on the problem, monitoring of the process of teaching foreign language, generalization of the authors' own experience of teaching. The authors define an important role of modern media in the foreign language teaching and develop a program of teaching the English language to Bachelor students using media educational environment.

Keywords: foreign language, Bachelor students, Bachelor's program, media educational environment, professional communication.

Every citizen of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan must be able to read the original literature in a foreign language, understand the text and use it in their profession. He should also be able to communicate freely in a foreign language with his interlocutor on a given topic. After all, learning foreign languages is a requirement of today's globalized era.

Due to independence, special attention is paid to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. Thousands of foreign language teachers have been trained, all conditions have been created for staff training in our country and abroad, multimedia textbooks in English, German and French, electronic resources for learning English have been prepared. The organization of language rooms is a clear proof of this. On the basis of improving the education of the younger generation in foreign languages

and the training of specialists who are fluent in these languages a lot of work is being done.

Learning English is becoming a priority of the modern education system. Open cultural and social doors for those who speak this language are all open to economic doors, because the use of English creates more opportunities for reading and working. The latter is highly valued in the context of the competitiveness of each country's labor market. At a time when the development of science is accelerating, interdisciplinary integration plays a crucial role in the establishment of continuing education. The term integration is derived from the Latin word *integrare*, meaning to join, to unite. Data integration involves combining and presenting materials available from different sources for a specific purpose.

Integration, on the other hand, is based on interdisciplinary communication, that is, on the knowledge gained in general in the sciences, academic disciplines, their sections and topics. means opening. That integrated learning has its place in English language teaching we can observe. The teacher's child thinking and different areas its role in arousing interest also justifies itself in this approach.

From this interdisciplinary communication will also increase significantly. In various parts of the education system, pre-school children, primary school students (ages 7-11) and high school students are learning a foreign language. An integrated approach can be used in primary education along with game technology. For high school students, thinking is also a factor in broadening their horizons.

Management of computer networks such as the Internet is necessary in various production and leisure systems. Thus, there is a need to introduce these technologies into pedagogical practice as part of a new teaching strategy. Thus, the use of technology in the language teaching process leads to greater efficiency.

In order to integrate the solution of a problem based on interdisciplinary communication, the teacher must first clearly define the goal, review the material to be studied, select appropriate methods for its effective mastering, determine the form and organization of the lesson process and it is required to predetermine the results to be obtained.

What is the most important thing in improving your students ability of learning a foreign language? Through out the findings which I have found during the researches on teaching English crucial was that for many students isn't only new world, new way of life, new people and of course new opportunities but also the tool changing them mentally and

psychologically. So, how to involve your students in English learning atmosphere requires you much effort. Immersing your students in the target language helps them use it more independently and this can lead to increase confidence and better vocabulary. Students enjoy listening to ‘ real people ’ speaking the target language, so get our colleagues involved.

Firstly, you can start with encouraging students and staff to use the language. Even if they make mistakes, and emphasize that communication is the key. You could invite a fluent speaker into the classroom, perhaps a friend or a colleague from another school, as a guest. Anything show the target language being used in practical situations will emphasize the value of the language as a communicative tool. If we take into consideration grammar, grammar translation method lately has been considered as an old method of teaching and it has also advantages. Grammar is the foundation for building language skills. Learning grammar enables students to speak and write more accurately, confidently and fluently. I have found that asking students to explain grammar rules to each other and to the rest of the class gives them more confidence. The more you learn, use and practice the language , the more accurate and fluent you become. Repetition and practice are essential to many skills , and this is especially true when learning a language. I want to indicate that one of the best ways to learn English is reading. Reading is a learned skill, but good reading relies on more than how we were taught to read. Reading improves writing, writing improves reading. Also, by reading you revise widen what you know and learn what you weren't aware of before.

All things considered, the more you learn and teach , use and practice the language , the more accurate and fluent your students become. Repetition and practice are essential to many skills, and this is especially true when learning a language.

Given the goals and objectives of teaching English in higher education, they can be divided into 2 groups:

1. Foreign language - universities, institutes, faculties that train specialists in English.
2. Foreign language - non-philological education that does not train a specialist in English institutions.

The goals of teaching English in these 2 groups are different, and in the first group of higher education institutions, English is taught in depth, both theoretically and practically, due to the training of English language specialists. In the second group, non-philological educational institutions, there is a complex goal in English. The goal is for the student to receive a

general education in English and to teach him / her to use English in his / her future work in his / her specialty. Partial communication in the profession involves learning to read and translate texts by learning words related to their specialty.

Teaching foreign languages in higher education institutions includes 1) practical or communicative, 2) general education, 3) education, 4) the use of acquired skills and abilities for other purposes, development goals. General educational, pedagogical and developmental goals occur in the realization of the communicative goal. Let's take a closer look at these 4 goals:

1. Communicative (practical) goal: Through this goal, students develop skills in English language materials. Students lexical, grammatical pronunciation should be able to apply the materials independently in speech. English speaking, reading, writing skills are developed.

2. General educational purpose: Through this purpose to further develop students' thinking, to receive and impart information in English, to gain a deeper understanding of English, new knowledge of English and the history and literature of the people of the country where the language is studied and broadening students 'worldviews through the acquisition of insights and information about their culture. Students 'understanding, growth of thinking, broadening of their worldview will be at the expense of a foreign language or in English.

3. Educational goal: This goal is to provide international, moral and aesthetic education in a foreign language English class, as well as to cultivate an attitude to work.

4. Developmental goal: This goal defines the guidelines for learning, teaching students to know the student personally. It develops language analysis, generalization, independent reasoning, listening, speech, and movement skills. It teaches to imagine, to create a speech situation, to have a logical connection in speech, to be able to think independently, to understand the meaning of words, to work independently with a dictionary, manuals, and to take optional classes, develops independent preparation for extracurricular activities, their conduct. The four goals above are always complementary, in touch with each other. These four goals should be achieved through English language materials, speech activities, taught and repeated in each lesson.

Upon graduation, students are required to be able to accept, comprehend, and articulate an English opinion orally and in writing.

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